

Three Phases of the Deer Ked (*Lipoptena cervi*) Attack on Humans: Field and Genetic Studies

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Abstract / Graphical abstract

This paper describes three stages of the deer ked (*Lipoptena cervi*) attack on humans—a victim that the deer ked mistakes for its usual hosts, i.e., forest mammals. The work combines field research, genetic studies, a literature review, and observations in forests around Iława (Poland). It details how the deer ked locates its victim by sight, then corrects its course using thermal sensors that detect warm places, and subsequently moves around on the host to select a site for piercing. The paper also examines the presence in the deer ked genome of traditional thermoreceptor genes as well as those potentially aiding in processing information about external temperature.

Figure 1. First phase of the attack. A deer ked approaches the host from a distance.

Figure 2. A deer ked orients to warmer areas on the host (second phase of the attack)

Figure 3. Third phase of the attack. The deer ked is looking for a place to bite.

Introduction

The deer ked (*Lipoptena cervi*) (1) has been increasingly observed in forests around Iława and elsewhere in Poland for several years. Although humans are not its intended hosts and bites are rare, this insect does land on people. Since its bites can be painful, it may transmit diseases, and simply crawling on the skin is irritating, it deserves attention. In this text, I describe the three stages of the deer ked attack, based on my own experiences, independent field studies, a literature review, and my own genetic research.

The deer ked follows three attack phases. In the first, it flies directly toward its target based on a visual pattern match. In the second, once close to the target, it adjusts its flight using heat sensors to pick warmer areas. After landing, it looks for a spot under the hair where it can attach well, and only then does it pierce the skin.

I. Behavior of the Deer Ked in Contact with Humans

The deer ked feeds on blood. Young individuals leave the female's body with energy reserves that must last until they find a host. They attack humans by mistake, confusing them with forest mammals. Once landed, they can search for a feeding spot on a human for over an hour, sometimes discarding their wings. Biting attempts in the first hour or two are rare. We can assume that the insect generally does not find on a human the conditions that its receptors would identify as optimal—conditions that would coincide with those found on its typical host.

1. First Stage of the Attack – Vision

Deer keds take off from bushes and trees, flying toward the target from as far as a few dozen meters. This can be seen in those rare moments when one's eyesight briefly focuses on the approaching insect, allowing an estimate of where it emerged from. I estimate its flight speed at about 40 km/h.

The deer ked has relatively large eyes, which, together with its nervous system, allow it to roughly classify the target. I conducted observations to see whether the deer ked is attracted by smell or carbon dioxide, but attacks occurred from directions downwind, where odor could not have traveled. Hence, I infer that the visual stimulus is the primary signal initiating flight, although I did not exclude other factors (either auxiliary or the only ones if, for instance, the target is motionless). I found no evidence that it uses heat from a distance of several or a few dozen meters.

I did not focus on color sensitivity, though it is possible that they notice dark green objects less often and rarely land on white ones. The frequency of attacks on humans suggests that the species as a whole does not visually distinguish humans from its usual cervid hosts.

Figure 4. Eye of a deer ked

2. Second Stage of the Attack – Heat

As it approaches its host, the insect appears to use heat sensing to adjust its flight toward warmer spots, although it is not very precise in determining where to land.

For a long time, I have observed that deer keds tend to land on exposed skin far more often than on clothing, suggesting that they may be guided by heat. However, this mechanism is not perfect. To study this, I walked through the forest wearing plastic rain ponchos and nitrile gloves.

I wore a green poncho (dark, forest color) and white gloves, as well as a yellow poncho and blue gloves. In the first outfit, deer keds landed on me far less frequently, but this might have been due to the places I walked. The preference was quite noticeable, yet it needs further study.

I had a glove on my left hand, whereas on my right hand I wore a heat-protective glove. In that hand, I held a 20 cm cardboard tube with a glove filled with polystyrene foam (ambient temperature) at the end. On my head I had a hood and a cap, but only the cap's visor protected my face.

In one documented observation (recorded), during approximately 20 minutes, deer keds landed:

- 16 times on my left hand
- 13 times on the front part of the poncho visible to me (chest area, above and below, without a camera view from behind) and on exposed face
- 10 times on the right-side contraption (including 6 closer to the heat source on the tube or on the heat-protective glove)

This indicates a clear preference for a heat gradient.

Earlier, I had conducted tests with a hot-water bottle at about 50–70°C in a fabric cover. However, this “super-signal” did not seem to attract more insects than normal body temperature.

Figure 5. Field research – left hand in a glove, right hand - not visible, wearing a thermal glove, holding a glove filled with polystyrene foam on a cardboard tube.

Sometimes the insect lands on objects near a heat source. It cannot always land directly on the heat source. It appears to fly toward warmth, and if it is off by half a meter or a meter, it will then move from the poncho (where it initially landed) onto the hand. I noticed several instances of such movement.

a) Anatomy of Sensors (including Heat Sensors)

The literature contains scans/photos of sensors in related species (*Melophagus ovinus*, *Hippobosca equina*, *Hippobosca longipennis*). (2)

Among these sensors, there appear to be those that could detect heat. Most thermosensitive neurons that register environmental temperature in insects are located on the antennae in cuticular structures called peg-in-pit sensilla. These sensilla typically contain three receptor neurons: one thermosensitive neuron and two opposing hygro-sensory neurons (3), or two chemosensory neurons. (4)

Melophagus ovinus (the sheep ked) (2) has no wings and thus presumably lacks well-developed sensors for the first two attack stages. It does not have large eyes, and its antennae are similar in size to the other two species. Concerning coeloconic sensilla, all three species have structures of similar size. However, the sheep ked has smaller basiconic sensilla and possesses three times fewer of both types of sensilla compared to the winged species. This could confirm that similar yet winged insects use heat sensors.

b) Genetics of Heat Sensors

In this study, I set out to determine whether the deer ked genome contains genes that might be responsible for detecting the host's heat or assist in that process. I chose genes potentially involved in heat perception in various insects (focusing on mosquitoes, ticks, blood-feeding bugs—Triatominae, and fruit flies—using various references). I selected: **GR28b.d, TRPA1, TRPA5, TRPA52, IR21a, Ir93a, Ir25a, Ir40a, nAChRalpha6, Dh31-R, Pdfr, Pyrexia, Painless, ppk24, ppk25**. These include both classic thermoreceptors and genes that may modulate temperature responses.

In the initial phase of research, given the lack of a published *Lipoptena cervi* genome, I examined four genes: TRPa1, IR25a, ppk25, Ir93a in a similar species' genome available online (5).

I obtained orthologs of these genes from the NCBI Gene database (NCBI Orthologs – transcripts FASTA – insects), and for TRPA52 from <https://www.orthodb.org/>. In the Galaxy platform (6), I aligned them using MAFFT, then built an HMM profile. I used the NHMMER program to search for homologous nucleotide sequences. All four tested genes were found in the camel ked (*Hippobosca camelina*), so it seemed reasonable to acquire the genome of deer keds living in our forest and examine their genes.

DNA isolated from a female deer ked from a forest near Ilawa was sent to a laboratory for sequencing. From the resulting data, I assembled the genome to the contig stage and conducted a bioinformatic analysis as described above (MAFFT-HMM-NHHMER).

I found strong matches in the deer ked for the genes GR28b.d, TRPA1, IR21a, Ir93a, Ir25a, Ir40a, nAChRalpha6, Dh31-R, Pdfr, Pyrexia, Painless, ppk24, and ppk25, while TRPA5 showed a weak match. TRPA52 was not found.

As a check, I used the same method to search for orthologs of Pla2 (phospholipase A2) genes in Hymenoptera, and these were also detected. Similarly, the SDIC2 gene, considered rare among insects, was found. Meanwhile, the algorithm did not detect the TRAC gene, which occurs in vertebrates with adaptive immunity but not in insects, nor LOC123006589 (GCA_015345945.1) typical of *Tribolium madens*, confirming that it only retrieves genuinely existing genes in the studied organism. It is worth noting that genes of different dipteran species can be similar in up to three-quarters of cases: “In total, 9172 (74%) of *Glossina* genes (from 8374 orthologous clusters) had a Dipteran ortholog,” (7). Detecting these genes indicates that thermal targeting of a host by the deer ked is not ruled out. This is further supported by the receptor structure in related species and the observed reactions of the insects. Further research could provide greater certainty.

3. Third Stage of the Attack – Attachment to Dense, Thick Hair and Piercing

Once deer keds find a host, they discard their wings and stay on it. On humans, they sometimes discard their wings while searching for a safe spot, and other times they search without discarding them. On exposed human skin, they mostly walk forward, but sometimes move sideways, at an angle, or in circles. Their initial walking speed can reach 30 cm per minute, then slows down. My assumption (not specifically tested) is that the deer ked looks for a place where it can firmly grip hair of an appropriate thickness (within the grasp of its tarsal claws, presumably thicker than human hair), possibly using signals from other sensors whose role is not fully investigated. While searching for a place, deer keds crawl under clothing. During various tests and observations, I felt a deer ked bite only once—about an hour after completing my fieldwork. The bite was very subtle (I would not have felt it while in the field), like a trial bite. I immediately found the deer ked under my clothing. No mark remained at the bite site, neither immediately nor later. I did not test longer periods—once I come back from the forest, I change clothes and shower. Possibly after a few hours, it would finally have pierced the skin. In the hair, it is fairly easy to detect and remove it when it starts to irritate the skin. This study did not include detailed examination of this attack stage.

Figure 6. Tarsal claws and pulvillus of the deer ked

Figure 7. Tarsal claws of the deer ked

2. Additional Information

The insect harbors a symbiont (*Arsenophonus lipopteni*) that enables it to obtain vitamin B from the host's blood. The tsetse fly (*Wigglesworthia glossinidia brevipalpis*) has a similar symbiont. I compared the genes of these symbionts (using genomes from the NCBI database visualized in Mauve). I also performed a second comparison in Mauve with the aphid symbiont *Buchnera aphidicola*, where the genetic similarity is low. More information is available at:

<https://www.przewodnik.ilawa.pl/bezpiecze%C5%84stwo-w-lesie/strzy%C5%BCak-jeleni-a-mucha-tse-tse>

Figure 8. Comparison of the genomes of *Arsenophonus lipopteni* and *Wigglesworthia glossinidia brevipalpis*. Shared genes are marked with colors

Figure 9. Comparison of the genomes of *Arsenophonus lipopteni* and *Buchnera aphidicola*. Shared genes are marked with colors.

Conclusions

Field research and a literature review on sensors in related species seem to confirm, and genetic research provides no evidence against, the hypothesis that the deer ked primarily uses vision in its attack (first phase), then host heat (second phase), and finally other stimuli (third phase).

It remains untested whether deer keds use heat detection to choose more precise feeding sites on the host's body, or whether this is a feature shared with related species that parasitize smaller mammals and which does not offer significant benefits against larger forest mammals—but accidentally becomes more noticeable when attacking humans.

Longer field trials on a larger sample of insects, designed with similar research techniques, could successfully provide more conclusive information about these behavioral traits of the deer ked.

This study should be regarded as a preliminary test supporting the hypothesis derived from observations.

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- **Forest Guide – Ilawa and the Surroundings of Jeziorak** (www.przewodnik.ilawa.pl)

The research was funded solely from own resources.

I can share the readings and assembled contigs for non-commercial research – please contact: instytutidei@gmail.com

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest. The author produces a deer ked repellent and conducts research on improving this product; however, the scope of that research is not included in this paper, and its results remain confidential to the author. Profits from the product sales partially fund the author's educational and research activities, as well as those of the Ilavian Institute of Ideas.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asd.2008.11.001>

(Referring to Waldow, 1970; Tichy, 1979; Altner et al., 1981; Altner & Loftus, 1985)

(4) Markus Ruchty, Roberto Romani, Linda S. Kuebler, Sara Ruschioni, Flavio Roces, Nunzio Isidoro, Christoph J. Kleineidam (2009) “The thermo-sensitive sensilla coeloconica of leaf-cutting ants (*Atta vollenweideri*),”

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(Referring to Altner et al., 1977, 1981; Davis, 1977; Hansson et al., 1996)

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isci.2024.109541>

Supplementary Material

ANNEX 1 -- Methodology of Genetic Research

Based on the genome sizes of similar species, the length was estimated at 130 million base pairs. Due to budget limitations, long reads were not used; only short-read sequencing was ordered (we still have a sample available for long reads if funding becomes available).

From the insect (female), 6 legs were taken, and then DNA was isolated using the AAbiot Bead-Beat Micro AX Gravity kit.

The DNA was sent to an external laboratory, which performed Quality Control, Library Preparation, and Sequencing (Read length: 2 x 100 bp, Output: 15 Gb per sample). The result was provided in two FASTQ files.

Information from the laboratory:

Number of reads (in million): 169.439

Number of bases (in GB): 16.977

Library preparation (DNA): Quantity used: 41.00 ng

The isolate was below the necessary concentration (10 ng/μl)

Library preparation kit: Illumina DNA Prep, (M) Tagmentation

Q30 value of sequencing (DNA): 89.42%

Sequencing parameters (DNA): NovaSeq 6000, 2 x 101 bp

BIOINFORMATIC ANALYSIS

Demultiplexing: Demultiplexing of the sequencing reads was performed with Illumina bcl2fastq (version 2.20).

Adapters were trimmed with Skewer (version 0.2.2) (Jiang et al. 2014). Quality trimming of the reads has not been performed.

The MultiQC report was generated using MultiQC version 1.22.2

The quality of the FASTQ files was analyzed using FastQC on Illumina's DRAGEN Bio-IT Platform (version 4.2.4). Plots were created using ggplot2 (Wickham 2009) in R (version 4.0.4) (R Core Team 2015).

Genome assembly was carried out on the <https://usegalaxy.eu/> platform.

The first step was reanalysis of the FASTQ files.

Next, filtering was performed with FASTP

(Number of reads decreased by 5%; Total number of bases decreased by 0.6%)

KRAKEN 2: no contamination detected

The genome was assembled with MEGAHIT v.1.2.9.

(list of kmer sizes: 21,29,39,59,79,99,119)

BUSCO report:

```
# BUSCO version is: 5.8.0
```

```
# The lineage dataset is: insecta_odb10 (Creation date: 2024-01-08, number of genomes: 75, number of BUSCOs: 1367)
```

```
# Summarized benchmarking in BUSCO notation for file
```

```
/data/dnb10/galaxy_db/files/d/c/c/dataset_dcca98b3-f769-4c1c-836a-ffc6770c6c3d.dat
```

```
# BUSCO was run in mode: euk_genome_aug
# Gene predictor used: augustus

***** Results: *****
C:97.3%[S:96.4%,D:0.9%],F:1.5%,M:1.2%,n:1367
1330 Complete BUSCOs (C)
1318 Complete and single-copy BUSCOs (S)
12 Complete and duplicated BUSCOs (D)
20 Fragmented BUSCOs (F)
17 Missing BUSCOs (M)
1367 Total BUSCO groups searched
Assembly Statistics:
38637 Number of scaffolds
38637 Number of contigs
207969753 Total length
0.000% Percent gaps
14 KB Scaffold N50
14 KB Contigs N50
```

ANNEX 2 -- HMMER Sequence Search Results

Results of searching for individual gene sequences in the deer ked genome. HMMER was used, which can detect more distant nucleotide homologies than BLAST.

Dh31-R

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
5.7e-73	247.2	24.2	k119_85004	9555	10120	flag=1 multi=17.7249 len=17242
4.5e-36	124.8	18.5	k119_85004	1913	2201	flag=1 multi=17.7249 len=17242
8.3e-27	94.0	4.5	k119_85004	15934	16065	flag=1 multi=17.7249 len=17242
1.7e-26	93.0	3.8	k119_85004	10915	11041	flag=1 multi=17.7249 len=17242
2e-24	86.1	3.3	k119_80611	6662	6769	flag=1 multi=16.9466 len=11215
3.3e-18	65.5	17.0	k119_85004	10567	10743	flag=1 multi=17.7249 len=17242

ppk25-LOC1276201

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
2e-138	464.3	94.7	k119_77291	12627	10250	flag=0 multi=18.7743 len=24281
1.3e-11	43.7	17.0	k119_18783	4929	4781	flag=0 multi=20.9598 len=10067

IR25a

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
0	1282.4	47.5	k119_82934	9688	8515	flag=0 multi=22.8673 len=12889
2.7e-98	330.2	28.5	k119_82934	11501	11027	flag=0 multi=22.8673 len=12889
2.5e-63	214.2	25.4	k119_82934	8420	7989	flag=0 multi=22.8673 len=12889
5.2e-46	156.7	29.9	k119_82934	10434	10015	flag=0 multi=22.8673 len=12889
2.9e-43	147.6	12.8	k119_82934	10926	10682	flag=0 multi=22.8673 len=12889
5.7e-10	37.1	12.5	k119_25479	1665	1448	flag=0 multi=47.8344 len=5794

Ir93a

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
3.3e-97	327.2	115.5	k119_31031	26931	25679	flag=0 multi=21.7164 len=36701
3.5e-88	297.3	85.8	k119_31031	22293	21333	flag=0 multi=21.7164 len=36701
3.7e-32	111.4	18.3	k119_31031	23526	23173	flag=0 multi=21.7164 len=36701
1.1e-22	79.9	19.5	k119_31031	27884	27587	flag=0 multi=21.7164 len=36701
1.3e-18	66.4	15.9	k119_31031	25589	25460	flag=0 multi=21.7164 len=36701

trpa1

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
5.8e-277	923.5	49.8	k119_12166	3834	2642	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
1.2e-90	305.1	60.4	k119_12166	2529	1653	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
3.7e-70	237.1	39.2	k119_367	6018	5482	flag=0 multi=11.7732 len=8067
1e-57	195.8	30.9	k119_12166	1581	1205	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
9.1e-49	166.1	4.2	k119_12166	6758	6563	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
5.6e-41	140.3	11.1	k119_12166	10554	10351	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
1.2e-29	102.7	5.8	k119_367	6212	6096	flag=0 multi=11.7732 len=8067
3.9e-22	77.7	7.3	k119_12166	13301	13141	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320
1.6e-20	72.3	5.0	k119_12166	8891	8783	flag=0 multi=20.8213 len=23320

GR28b.d

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
1.7e-73	248.7	45.1	k119_1025	10784	11184	flag=0 multi=20.6069 len=22870
1.3e-21	76.5	15.2	k119_1025	11274	11427	flag=0 multi=20.6069 len=22870
3.3e-13	48.7	50.3	k119_1025	9643	10050	flag=0 multi=20.6069 len=22870
3.4e-09	35.3	41.6	k119_1025	12796	13139	flag=0 multi=20.6069 len=22870
1.4e-05	23.3	8.6	k119_1145	14751	14825	flag=0 multi=20.6384 len=39016

Ir40a

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
1.7e-72	245.9	22.9	k119_26555	6911	6324	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
9.8e-55	187.0	23.2	k119_26555	3929	3301	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
1.6e-54	186.4	8.8	k119_26555	5424	5195	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
4.8e-38	131.7	45.8	k119_26555	8708	8248	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
1.6e-37	129.9	13.2	k119_26555	7308	6985	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
2.1e-27	96.4	11.8	k119_26555	8183	8015	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499
2.9e-26	92.6	15.3	k119_26555	4804	4623	flag=0 multi=20.1942 len=26499

ppk24

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
0	2119.9	3.8	XM_001953446.4	3	3080	PREDICTED: Drosophila ananassae sodium channel...
0	2084.8	4.6	XM_039375737.1	11	2607	PREDICTED: Drosophila yakuba sodium channel...
0	2058.3	0.2	XM_039295425.2	266	2880	PREDICTED: Drosophila simulans sodium channel...

...(Truncated for brevity; full table continues)

TRPA5 - Apis mellifera (weak match)

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
3e-05	22.0	0.4	k119_43356	4965	4820	flag=0 multi=20.8037 len=35080
0.00098	16.9	0.6	k119_65853	24664	24748	flag=0 multi=22.9842 len=27900

TRPA5 (Manduca sexta) - weak match

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
0.0024	17.8	14.4	k119_71252	19415	19694	flag=1 multi=21.9776 len=107650

Ira21a

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
8.7e-131	439.3	89.2	k119_34605	15441	14286	flag=0 multi=20.9846 len=31099
5.4e-103	347.0	28.5	k119_34605	14228	13840	flag=0 multi=20.9846 len=31099
5.5e-77	260.7	32.1	k119_34605	12332	11848	flag=0 multi=20.9846 len=31099
4.5e-35	121.7	16.5	k119_34605	12600	12402	flag=0 multi=20.9846 len=31099
0.0088	14.5	31.2	k119_64893	2952	3473	flag=0 multi=15.7706 len=11432

PYX, Pyrexia

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
1.8e-281	939.0	64.4	k119_71252	17394	18835	flag=1 multi=21.9776 len=107650
8.5e-136	455.5	45.6	k119_71252	15652	16854	flag=1 multi=21.9776 len=107650
5.4e-125	419.6	83.8	k119_71252	19409	20481	flag=1 multi=21.9776 len=107650

...

PDFR

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
9.4e-170	567.6	82.9	k119_85338	20200	18196	flag=0 multi=21.9873 len=34736
5.3e-67	226.8	27.6	k119_85338	21503	21028	flag=0 multi=21.9873 len=34736
3.4e-19	68.2	2.1	k119_85338	21782	21670	flag=0 multi=21.9873

len=34736

...

Pain, Painless

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
3.2e-253	845.1	156.6	k119_43961	4093	2023	flag=1 multi=19.9926
len=44314						
7.8e-30	103.8	76.0	k119_43961	1941	991	flag=1 multi=19.9926
len=44314						
1.6e-15	56.3	2.9	k119_57219	20569	20284	flag=0 multi=22.0000
len=33404						
...						

nAChRalpha6

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
3.2e-253	845.1	156.6	k119_43961	4093	2023	flag=1 multi=19.9926
len=44314						
7.8e-30	103.8	76.0	k119_43961	1941	991	flag=1 multi=19.9926
len=44314						
1.6e-15	56.3	2.9	k119_57219	20569	20284	flag=0 multi=22.0000
len=33404						
...						

TRPA52 (Nilaparvata lugens)

No hits detected that satisfy reporting thresholds.

Others (program test):

TRAC - not found.

LOC123006589 (GCA-015345945.1) - not found.

SDIC2

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
5.1e-68	233.9	16.1	k119_3758	2176	1709	flag=0 multi=21.9837
len=25863						
1.8e-58	202.3	15.8	k119_3758	1627	1119	flag=0 multi=21.9837
len=25863						
7.5e-47	163.8	18.6	k119_3758	2807	2252	flag=0 multi=21.9837
len=25863						

SPOOK

E-value	score	bias	Sequence	start	end	Description
1.1e-26	97.2	47.1	k119_54314	19645	20517	flag=0 multi=23.2863
len=41518						
2.5e-11	46.3	13.4	k119_54314	18426	18684	flag=0 multi=23.2863
len=41518						

Pla2 - phospholipase A2 - matches found.

End of Annexes.